

ISic0826

I.Sicily inscription 0826

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication (?)

Material

stone

(black)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [τοῦ]ου τοῦ
2. κλαρονόμου
3. [Σ]τρατίππου
4. καὶ ἸΣΕΙ[---]

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492452

EDCS 39101976

PHI 140296

Bibliography

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliæ obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.94

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0006 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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